

TREATMENT STRATEGIES FOR PATIENTS WITH ADVANCED STAGE PARKINSON'S DISEASE

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ABSTRACT Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder affecting multiple systems and mainly related to dopaminergic deficiency in the substantia nigra resulting in bradykinesia, rigidity and rest tremor. Pharmacological treatments are very successful in the early stages of the disease, but side effects and motor complications are the main problems as the disease reaches to advanced stage. In advanced PD patients, the most disabling complication of long term L-dopa treatment is the unpredictable swings between "on" state with L-dopa induced dyskinesias and "off" state. We will review the current pharmacological and surgical treatment options in advanced stage of PD. The major benefits of deep brain stimulation (DBS) are to smooth motor fluctuations and/or dyskinesia who does not achieve satisfactory symptom control with optimized medical therapy; patients with medically refractory tremor; who are intolerant of dopaminergic drugs; or the patients with a combination of these issues should be considered for DBS surgery. In recent years physical therapy focusing on gait and balance gained more importance.

The advanced PD patients are good candidate for DBS. DBS can improve "on" time, reduce on-off fluctuations, and decrease levodopa-induced dyskinesias but, with the exception of tremor, does not provide motor benefits that exceed the patient's best "on" medication state and emphasizing the contribution of new perspectives of physical therapies on motor functioning that enhance positive impacts of medical and surgical treatments.

KEYWORDS Parkinson's disease; L-dopa treatment; Deep brain stimulation (DBS); Physical therapies

Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder affecting multiple systems and mainly related to a dopaminergic deficiency in the substantia nigra resulting in bradykinesia, rigidity and rest tremor. The therapy of PD has been a challenge for a neurologist for a long time. Pharmacological treatments are very successful in the early stages of the disease, but side effects and motor complications are the main problems as the disease reaches to an advanced stage. In

advanced PD patients, the most disabling complication of long-term L-dopa treatment is the unpredictable swings between an "on" state with L-dopa induced dyskinesias and "off" state. Additionally, patients suffer from the reduced duration of L-dopa response, dose failures and dose variability in response [1]. Pharmacological adjustments are usually unsatisfactory in controlling these motor complications, thus progressively compromising quality of life [2]. Bilateral high-frequency stimulation of either subthalamic nucleus (STN) or globus pallidus interna (GPi) is one of the most effective procedures currently available for alleviating the disabling motor symptoms and complications in advanced PD. Deep brain stimulation (DBS) of both targets improves tremor, limb rigidity, bradykinesia and akinesia [3,4]. In this paper, we will review the current pharmacological and surgical treatment options in an advanced stage of PD, emphasizing the contribution of new perspectives of physical therapies on motor functioning that enhance positive impacts of medical and surgical treatments.

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Motor complications in advanced stage PD

Clinicians define advanced PD as stage 4 and five on the Hoehn and Yahr scale which means the onset of motor complications, despite aggressive pharmacological and behavioural management [5]. In this stage, patients may notice a decline in motor benefit several hours after the last dose of L-dopa ("end of dose deterioration" or "wearing off phenomenon"). Several potential mechanisms collectively lead to a narrow therapeutic window where low plasma and striatal levels of dopaminergic drugs will lead to "off" periods and high levels will lead to choreiform involuntary movements emerging within 1-2 hours after L-dopa intake ("peak-dose dyskinesia"). Later, dyskinesias may also occur at the onset and offset of motor benefit ("diphasic dyskinesias"). It has been estimated that motor complications occur 50% of patients by five years of disease [6]. In later stages of PD, patients who suffer from motor complications usually need assistance for most of their daily activities such as feeding, personal hygiene, dressing, turning in bed, rising from the seating position and walking. Moreover, gait disturbances, especially "freezing of gait" and postural instability are more frequent in the advanced stage that leads to frequent falls and increases the risk fractures.

Medical management of motor complications

In the management of motor complications, neurologists should first focus on the optimization of dopaminergic drugs and issues like drug absorption, timing, dosages and pharmacokinetic and delivery changes should be reevaluated. For instance, a protein-rich diet can lead to delayed absorption of L-dopa, and this can be improved by taking the pills one half to one hour before meals [7]. Fractionating the daily L-dopa dose into smaller, more frequent doses and administering liquid L-dopa formulations can increase drug absorption as well, and reduce "off" period and peak dose dyskinesias [8]. Amantadine (100-300 mg/day) may also help to suppress peak-dose dyskinesias. Wearing off symptoms are usually managed by combining L-dopa with a catechol-o-methyl transferase inhibitor (entacapone), a dopaminergic agonist or an MAO-B inhibitor (selegiline). Another option is adding a slow release L-dopa preparation especially at bedtime can help to relieve nocturnal akinesia and early morning dystonia.

Most of the time manipulating the oral drug regimen is enough to manage motor fluctuations and dyskinesia, but in some PD patients, severe motor fluctuations and peak dose dyskinesias make it necessary to use alternative routes of drug deliver or consider DBS surgery. Continuous dopaminergic stimulation with subcutaneous apomorphine injections can help to reduce daily "off" periods of about 50%, but side effects, like hypotension and skin nodules, can be troublesome. Another alternative route of L-dopa delivery is achieved by percutaneous gastrostomy (PEG). This system directly delivers concentrated gel preparations of L-dopa-carbidopa (Duodopa [Solvay Pharmaceuticals, Hannover, Germany]) into jejunum and can help to reduce motor complications by attaining more stable plasma L-dopa levels.

Surgical management of motor complications

Unfortunately, as the disease progress, therapeutic benefit window gradually narrows and patients are severely disabled due to frequent and severe shifts between "off" periods and "on" periods with peak-dose dyskinesias. In recent years DBS has

become an critical symptomatic treatment in the management of dopamine resistant tremor and motor fluctuations due to long-term dopaminergic treatment. Ten to 20% of PD patients are eligible for deep brain stimulation [9]. The significant benefits of DBS are to smooth motor fluctuations and dyskinesia who does not achieve satisfactory symptom control with optimized medical therapy; patients with medically refractory tremor; who are intolerant of dopaminergic drugs; or the patients with a combination of these issues should be considered for DBS surgery. However, the presences of significant cognitive impairment, refractory psychiatric or medical co-morbidities are the main contraindications for DBS and may influence the decision to proceed. There are several available surgical methods. In the most common method, DBS surgery is performed in two stages. After the patient's preparations have been completed, the stereotactic frame is placed on the head under local anaesthesia. The patients are transferred to the computed tomography (CT) scanning or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) suite for image acquisition and then to the operation room for the surgery. The targeting is based on magnetic resonance images (MRI) or merged with CT. Then, neurosurgeons plan the target coordinates and lead trajectory. The subthalamic nucleus (STN), globus pallidus interna (GPi), the pedunculopontine nucleus (PPN), zona incerta and ventro-intermediate nucleus (Vim) are five possible targets chosen (10). These structures play critical roles in the control of movement. Patients are positioned for surgery in the head holder. After a standard incision, burr holes, trajectory, macroelectrode and microelectrode recordings for targets are performed; then, the DBS electrode is inserted in the awake patient who had satisfactory improvement of symptoms and an adequate threshold for side effects such as strength, vision, and improvement of motor function. The process is repeated on the other hemisphere. In the second stage, the same day following the electrode implantation, the lead cable connectors and IPG are placed under general anaesthesia. DBS complications may be divided into risks associated with the surgical procedure and chronic complications of therapy that may or may not be device related [10]. The most severe complications of DBS surgery are stroke (0.9%), intracerebral haemorrhage (1.2%), seizure (1.2%), hardware-related complications such as device infection (4.4%), lead fracture (3.8%), skin erosion, and device migration or misplacement (3.2%), and the risks vary from study to study depending on many factors [11, 12]. These risks may be somewhat attenuated by appropriate screening and treatment of comorbid conditions, including hypertension, which increases hemorrhage risk during microelectrode recording; diabetes, which increases the risk of infection; psychiatric disease, which increases the risk of depression and suicide; cognitive deficits, which increase the risk of postoperative confusion; and obesity or other significant cardiopulmonary diseases, which may increase the general risk of surgery [11].

Physiotherapy and rehabilitation

In recent years physical therapy focusing on gait and balance gained more importance. Interesting new perspectives are forthcoming on motor functioning to enhance the positive impacts of DBS. Physical therapies combined with DBS can help to preserve an appropriate level of activity, treat specific disabilities and establish new movement patterns.

Functional disorders caused by clinical symptoms lead to deterioration in activities of daily living and quality of life, depending on the severity of the disease. The physiotherapy program

Fig.1. Therapeutic process.

Fig.2. Physical therapy assessment and rehabilitation program in post-operative phase.

to be applied according to the needs of the patient in different phases of Parkinson's disease will also vary. Information about the treatment process of patients at different stages is summarized in Figure 1 [28].

Physiotherapy approaches, including exercise programs, play an essential role in the treatment of Parkinson's disease [29]. Increasingly, exercise programs have been shown to be highly effective in reducing functional deficits [30]. The most important goal of the rehabilitation program is to increase the mobility and functional capacity of the patient, to increase the quality of life, and to make social life return by increasing the level of independence. Physiotherapy and rehabilitation programs should not only aim to treat the functions that are impaired but also to prevent the problems that will arise. Beginning the physiotherapy program concurrently with the treatment of the disease from the early stages of the disease may help to avoid such problems that lead to dependence, inactivity, social isolation and reduced quality of life [31].

1. Preoperative Phase The aim of physiotherapy and rehabilitation in the preoperative stage is to prepare the patients who are undergoing DBS. The goal of physical therapy program are; improve the respiratory function and to prevent respiratory complications, decrease rigidity, reduce the pain, maintain independence, improve the flexibility; optimize gait, to recommended assistive devices, maximize gross motor coordination and balance, provide the safe ambulation, educate and guide caregiving needs [32, 33].

The first step of preoperative evaluation is to inform the patient and his/her family about the possible complications of the surgeon. The evaluation procedure to be performed before determining the appropriate rehabilitation program for the patient includes balance, mobility, tremor, rigidity, coordination, speech, evaluation of hand functions, activ-

ities of daily living, environmental assessment, assistive device selection [34].

2. Postoperative Phase After surgery, patients are assessed at first 24 hours following the battery setting. Parkinson's disease has a respiratory failure due to flexure posture, kyphosis and rigidity. After surgery, physiotherapy begins with breathing exercises. Respiratory exercises, postural alignment exercises, and upper body extension exercises are effective for increasing respiratory capacity [34, 35]. Post-operative evaluation and physiotherapy program to be performed are given in Figure 2.

To reduce postural disturbance and balance problems, the patient should be taught the correct posture. Postural extension exercises and trunk rotation movements should be applied. To prevent falls, the patient should be instructed to rotate around a large arc by correctly positioning the foot and increasing visual and verbal stimuli, while walking. Walking with a rhythm and proper walking with arm swings should be taught to prevent freezing [34, 35]. In Parkinsonian patients, speech problems are seen as a result of the fact that the respiratory frequency cannot be controlled at first, but later on, facial muscles are affected. Respiratory exercises, facial, oral and lingual muscle exercises should be performed to prevent aspiration by speech therapy and to ensure speech correctness [34]. The steps of the rehabilitation program that will occur after surgery are explained in detail in Figure 3 [28].

3. Recommendations for patients and family. Frequent rest periods should be given during exercises; excessive fatigue should be avoided.

The activities that patients should not do after surgery are as follows:

- Cervical manipulation, massage and excessive cervical exercise should be avoided.
- Upper limb activities above the head level should not be done.
- Do not lift more than 3-4 kg in the first month.
- Some medical devices such as MRI should not be used.
- Do not pass through electromagnetic gates.
- Wireless connections are dangerous for battery.
- Stay away from high-powered industrial machines.
- Simple sportive activities can be carried out, especially those that are not physically risky to crash and without contact with the tie or neuro-stimulator.

Rehabilitation practices should continue lifelong in Parkinson's disease. In this regard, directing patients to activities such as walking and dancing to improve aerobic capacities will facilitate the maintenance of the rehabilitation program [36]. Patient and family should be made aware. The exercises and suggestions should be given as a home program, for this purpose [36, 37].

Discussion

DBS surgery will potentially benefit only symptoms that are levodopa responsive [11]. However, the patients who have typical PD with tremor, dyskinesias, and wearing-off spells are a good candidate for DBS. DBS can improve "on" time, reduce on-off fluctuations, and decrease levodopa-induced dyskinesias (direct suppressive effect or indirectly by allowing some reduction in

Table 1 Treatment strategies

Stimulation of activities		
	Goal	Strategy
<i>Transfers</i>	Perform transfers (more) independently	Practice transfers by using cognitive movement strategies and on/off cues for movement initiation
<i>Body posture</i>	Conscious normalization of body posture	Practice relaxed and coordinated moving; providing feedback and advice
<i>Reaching and grasping</i>	Improve reaching and grasping, and manipulating and moving objects	Practice reaching and grasping by using cues and cognitive movement strategies
<i>Balance</i>	Improve balance during activities	Practice balance, train muscle strength (see the prevention of falls)
<i>Gait</i>	Improve walking (independently); the objective is to increase the (comfortable) walking speed; however, safety comes first	Practice walking by using cues for initiation and continuation of walking, give instruction and train muscle strength and trunk mobility
Prevention		
<i>Inactivity</i>	Preserve or improve physical condition	Provide information on the importance of moving and playing sports, training of physical capacity; muscle strength (with the emphasis on trunk and leg muscles); aerobic capacity; and joint mobility (among others thoracic kyphosis, axial rotation and length of muscles of calf and hamstrings).
<i>Pressure Sores</i>	Prevention of pressure sores	Give advice and adjust the patient's body posture in bed or wheelchair (possibly in consultation with an occupational therapist); (supervised) active exercises to improve cardiovascular condition and prevention of contractures
<i>Falls</i>	Decrease or prevent falls	List possible causes of falls using falls diary; provide information and advice; train strength, body posture, coordination and balance, attuned to the cause of problems with maintaining balance and the increased falls risk; decrease the fear to fall (if necessary) provide hip protectors.

medication dose), but, with the exception of tremor, does not provide motor benefits that exceed the patient's best "on" medication state (with the current available targets of STN or GPi) [11]. Symptoms that do not respond at all to levodopa usually do not improve significantly with DBS. Following DBS, there may be a reduction, but not elimination, of anti-Parkinsonian medications.

DBS of the STN and GPi have been shown to be the most effective brain targets. All cardinal symptoms including akinesia, rigidity, tremor, and postural instability improve in STN target. At this time, data show that both STN and GPi DBS are effective for most symptoms, and it is not clear if one is a better target. Some reports demonstrated that there were no significant differences in motor outcome between STN DBS and GPi DBS [13]. Katz et al. performed a multicenter study that randomized PD patients to either STN or GPi DBS found that stimulation at either target provided similar overall motoric benefits [14]. They classified 235 subjects by motor subtype: tremor dominant (TD), intermediate (I), or postural instability gait difficulty (PIGD), based on pre-DBS baseline UPDRS scores off-medication [14]. Their results showed that responsiveness to both GPi and STN DBS is similar among different PD motor subtypes, although the TD motor subtype may have a more significant response to GPi DBS concerning gait. PIGD patients obtained less overall benefit from stimulation [14]. Williams reported that advantages of the STN target include more medication reduction, less frequent battery changes, and a more favourable economic profile [15]. However, they also found that advantages of GPi include more robust dyskinesia suppression, easier programming, and greater flexibility in adjusting medications [15]. Vim stimulation is only effective for tremor, not for the other symptoms of PD. Vim DBS may sometimes be an option in older patients with unilateral tremor-dominant PD [13]. The PPN is an investigational new target that may be appropriate for patients with gait freezing [10]. Zona incerta is another potential target for tremor and other cardinal motor manifestations, and this remains under investigation [10]. Plaha et al. showed that the results of zona incerta DBS are a good improvement [16].

In appropriately selected patients with advanced PD, DBS of the subthalamic nucleus or globus pallidus interna significantly reduces "off" time motor symptoms, reduces dyskinesias and improves quality of life [17–20]. Furthermore, recent publications suggest that DBS is superior to best medical therapy to alleviate motor symptoms and improve quality of life [20, 21]. The beneficial effects of DBS on specific motor symptoms (such as tremor, bradykinesia and dyskinesias) appear to be long-lasting [17]. However, other symptoms, including gait dysfunction and falls, do not necessarily improve after DBS and may even worsen [22]. In PD patients postural instability and gait impairment are also significant problems which become increasingly severe as the disease progresses even though L-dopa treatment postural impairment is not adequately improved, implying the involvement of nondopaminergic pathways. Moreover, besides disease progression and dyskinesias, L-dopa may also be responsible for worsening of postural sway [23–26]. In other words, postural stability and gait impairment are more variably affected by medications and DBS. There are also conflicting reports on whether functional balance tests improve with DBS [27]. In recent years physical therapy focusing on gait and balance gained more importance. Physical therapies combined with DBS can help to preserve an appropriate level of activity, treat specific disabilities and establish new movement patterns. The advanced

PD patients are a good candidate for DBS. Interesting new perspectives are forthcoming on motor functioning to enhance the positive impacts of DBS. New perspectives of physical therapies on motor functioning enhance positive impacts of medical and surgical treatments.

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